

TEACHING METHODS IN THE SCHOOL.

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Abstract: This article discusses innovative methods of teaching students in the 21st century. This article's goals are to study how educators now comprehend changes in didactics for the use of cutting-edge teaching techniques. It will also provide a summary of those developments. The paper took into account four areas: the development of pedagogy as a discipline, an ecological approach to learning, the digital age and continuous changes, and innovations in learning. Figuratively speaking, the philosophy of education has two levels. Training, modular training, distance learning, value orientation, case studies, coaching, role-playing games, business games, action according to the model, creative groups, analysis of "blockages," work in pairs, reflection method, and rotation method are some of the most popular modern teaching techniques used today.

Keywords: teaching Method, private methods, techniques, verbal methods, visual methods, practical methods, pedagogical skills, educational system, lecture, seminar, training, modular learning, distance learning, value orientation, case study, coaching, educational material, new goals, private schools, training centers, similar organizations.

Методы обучения в школе.

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языков.

Аннотация: В данной статье рассматриваются инновационные методы обучения студентов в 21 веке. Целью этой статьи является изучение того, как

преподаватели теперь понимают изменения в дидактике для использования передовых методов обучения. В нем также будет представлена краткая информация об этих событиях. В работе учитывались четыре направления: развитие педагогики как дисциплины, экологический подход к обучению, цифровая эпоха и непрерывные изменения, инновации в обучении. Образно говоря, философия образования имеет два уровня. Обучение, модульное обучение, дистанционное обучение, ценностная ориентация, кейсы, коучинг, ролевые игры, деловые игры, действие по образцу, творческие группы, разбор «завалов», работа в парах, метод рефлексии, метод ротации. некоторые из самых популярных современных методов обучения, используемых сегодня.

Ключевые слова: метод обучения, частные методы, приемы, вербальные методы, наглядные методы, практические методы, педагогическое мастерство, система обучения, лекция, семинар, тренинг, модульное обучение, дистанционное обучение, ценностная ориентация, кейс, коучинг, учебный материал, новые цели, частные школы, учебные центры, подобные организации.

More than a dozen fundamental studies are devoted to teaching methods, on which the considerable success of the work of the teacher and the school as a whole, both in the theory of pedagogy and in private methods of teaching individual subjects. And despite this, the problem of teaching methods both in teaching theory and in real pedagogical practice remains very relevant and from time to time gives rise to heated discussions on the pages of the pedagogical press. They are explained by the incessant attempts of theoreticians-teachers to move from empirical descriptions of individual groups of methods to substantiation of the scientific system of teaching methods and explaining their essence on the basis of revealing the nature of the teaching method and developing the foundations for their classification. Methods are implemented in pedagogical reality in various forms: in specific actions, techniques, organizational forms, etc. At the same time, methods and techniques are not rigidly tied to each other. For example, in such techniques

as a conversation or working with a book, different teaching methods can be embodied. The conversation can be heuristic and implement a partial search method, or it can be reproductive in nature, implement the appropriate method and be aimed at memorization and consolidation. The same can be said about working with a book, and about excursions, etc. It is necessary to stipulate that, according to the logic inherent in different classifications of methods (which will be discussed later), the same types of activity can be assigned to different didactic categories. For example, the same conversation or work with a book can be classified according to one classification as techniques, according to another - as methods. At the same time, the number of teaching methods can increase indefinitely depending on the content of the educational material, new goals and, of course, on the creativity of the teacher, his pedagogical skills, and thus give individuality to the manner of his pedagogical activity. A variety of combinations of techniques make up teaching methods. The earliest classification is the division of teaching methods into teacher work methods (story, explanation, conversation) and student work methods (exercises, independent work).

A common is the classification of teaching methods according to the source of knowledge. According to this approach, there are:

- verbal methods (the source of knowledge is the oral or printed word);
- visual methods (observable objects, phenomena, visual aids are the source of knowledge);
- practical methods (students gain knowledge and develop skills by performing practical actions).

If we talk about the traditional educational system, then in the institutions corresponding to it, modern teaching methods can be found extremely rarely, but as for private schools, training centers and other similar organizations, new methods appear more and more often in their activities. Why these methods are credited with greater efficiency than traditional methods, you will learn from this lesson. But in addition to the advantages, we will also mention the main disadvantages of innovative methods, which should be paid no less attention to. To

begin with, we note that modern teaching methods, unlike traditional ones, are characterized by slightly different features, namely. Modern teaching methods are already in the process of being adapted to a specific pedagogical design. The development is based on a specific methodological and philosophical view of the author. The technological sequence of actions, operations and interactions is based on target settings, which are a clear expected result

The implementation of the methods involves the associated activities of teachers and students, which have a contractual basis and which take into account the principles of differentiation and individualization, as well as the optimal use of human and technical potential. Mandatory components should be communication and dialogues. Pedagogical methods are planned in stages and implemented sequentially. In addition, they should be feasible for any teacher, but guarantee the achievement of the goal by each student. An indispensable component of the methods are diagnostic procedures, which contain the tools, indicators and criteria necessary for measuring student performance. Among the most popular modern teaching methods today are: lecture, seminar, training, modular learning, distance learning, value orientation, case study, coaching.

Modern teaching methods in many cases may not have a psychological and pedagogical justification, which is why it is quite difficult to classify them in some unified way. But this does not prevent not only their application in educational activities, but also does not have any significant impact on the success of this application.

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